

A Study of Green Finance and the Indian Growth Story

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Abstract

Tackling climate change has become a pivotal factor of the country's growth story. A significant amount of investment is required to create a greener economy. Green financial instruments are designed to provide access to efficient sources of debt and equity in order to fund projects with sustainable development goals. The Government of India along, with the support of private plaand institutions has made it a national priority to achieve sustainable growth. This paper studies the concept of Green Finance in the Global context along with various green financial instruments. It also identifies the problems related to the Indian Green Finance and provides recommendations in the Indian context.

Keywords: Green Finance, renewable energy, green financial instruments

Introduction

Green Finance includes instrument or investment through equity, debt, grant, purchase & sale or risk management tool (for example: investment guarantee, insurance product or commodity, credit or interest rate derivative, etc.) The aim of green financing is to enhance financial flows from public, private and non-profit sector towards to areas ensuring sustainable development. It includes optimally managing the environmental and social risks, and invest in areas that ensure a decent rate of return along with environmental benefits thus delivering greater accountability. A country can promote green financing through its regulatory framework, providing public financial incentives, green financing alternatives from various sectors, bringing public sector financing decisions in congruence with environmental sustainable development, promoting green technologies, developing natural resource based green economies, increase the use of green bonds and other related measures.

Literature Review

1. **Flammer Caroline (2018)** “Corporate Green Bonds” studies the concept of corporate green bonds. It studies the evolution of corporate green bonds and provides an industry-wise and a country-wise breakdown.
2. **Wang, Yao and Zhi, Qiang (2016)** “The Role of Green Finance in Environmental Protection: Two Aspects of Market Mechanism and Policies” studies current status of green finance in the field of renewable energy and identifies the deficiencies. It

studies the development of market mechanism and policy formulation. It helps find a solution for effectively achieving the ecological balance.

3. **DuPont Carolyn; Levitt, James and Bilmes, Linda (2015)** “Green Bonds and Land Conservation: The Evolution of a New Financing Tool” studies current and potential use of green bonds. The analysis is based on various interviews with relate actors and two case studies.
4. **Chowdhury, Tasnim and Datta, Rajib and Mohajan, Haradhan (2013)** “Green finance is essential for economic development and sustainability” studies the concept of green finance in a broader context. It identifies the role of green finance in various projects and sectors like agriculture and banking. It also lists the features of green financial products.

Research Methodology

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the global scenario of Green Finance.
2. To identify various instruments of Green Finance.
3. To understand the limitations and solutions of green financing in the Indian context.

Nature and Scope of Data

The present study is descriptive in nature and makes use of Secondary Data. The data has been collected from various publications of Governmental Organizations and Banks.

I. Green Finance: Global Scenario

The journey of sustainable finance began from the Montreal Protocol and the formation of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. The Journal of the initiatives that followed is as follows (Table 1):

Year	Initiative
1987	Montreal Protocol
1988	IPCC established
1992	Rio Summit: UNFCCC established
1994	UNFCCC enters into force
1997	KYOTO Protocol Signed
2000	MDGs launched
2001	COP7 Marrakesh Accord
2005	COP11 KYOTO entered into force: REDD introduced
2007	COP13 Bali Roadmap
2009	Copenhagen Accord
2010	COP16 Cancun Accord
2012	DOHA Agreement
2015	SDGs Launched
2015	Sendai Framework
2015	Addis Ababa Action Agenda
2015	Paris Accord: First Universal Climate Agreement
2016	COP22 Marrakesh Accord
2016	Kigali Amendment to Montreal Protocol

Source: Climate Policy Initiative

This was a result of change in the regulations in Pacific Region and East Asia, slowdown in economic growth and a decrease in renewable costs.

Source: Climate Policy Initiative

In 2017 climate finance peaked to USD 612bn, this was mainly a result of capacity enhancement by China, US and India in new renewable energy along with increased public focus on land use and energy efficiency. However 2018 the levels decreased by 11% and reached to USD 546bn.

Source: Climate Policy Initiatives

This is the direct result of increased focus of regulation and initiatives towards sustainable activities.

Public finance had a share of 44% in the total flows with transport being the major gainer. Private finance is the major contributor with a share of 56%. Renewable energy included 85% of these flows with low carbon transport at 14% and 1% of the flows were directed toward other subsectors. There has been a drastic increase in the funding from commercial financial institutions.

Majority of the climate finance comes through market rate debt (USD 316bn for 2017/2018). Around 93% of the low-cost project debt comes from public finance (mainly through concessional loans for climate related projects). 29% of tracked climate finance comes through equity which averages around USD 169bn annually. 74% of this is balance sheet equity while the rest is invested at the project level. 5% of climate finance is through Grants mainly issued by the public sector. Non-OECD regions get 78% of these grants.

Source: Climate Policy Initiatives

93% (2017/18) of the flows amounting to USD 537bn were mitigation finance. Adaption finance stood at 5%. There has been a rapid increase in the low carbon transport. This is a result of increased public and corporate investment in rail and transit projects and a rise in EV purchased by households. EV charging infrastructure has also been given a boost. 58% of the global climate finance is in renewable energy (USD 337bn, 2017/18).

Source: Climate Policy Initiatives

There has been a significant increase in the adaption finance from 2015/16 to 2017/18. The highest beneficiary in this regard being water and waste management. Due to various challenges with adaption finance the data represent a partial estimate. There is ambiguity over the definition and other issues including accounting, restrictions pertaining to confidentiality and the lack of universally accepted impact metrics. There have been efforts to counter these hurdles however overall flow towards adaption and resilience still falls short of targets as specified in the Paris Agreement.

Graph 5 Estimated Climate-Adjusted Infrastructure Investment Needs in Developing Asia (2016-30)

Source: ADB. 2017 Catalyzing Green Finance. Manila.p.13; and ADB. 2017 Meeting Asia’s Infrastructure Needs. Manila. p. xiv.

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Public and Private Infrastructure Finance has the following elements

<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Sources:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public (e.g. savings, revenue or taxes) - Private (e.g. savings, check money, shares or stocks) 	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Actors:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National and sub national governments - State owned entities - International development Organizations - Institutional Development Organizations - Institutional Investors - Private Investors - Philanthropic Organizations - Individuals and Civil Society
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Instruments:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equity - Debt - Grant - Risk Mitigation 	

II. Green Financial Instruments

Debt

1. Green Corporate Bonds: These bonds are used for climate and environmental projects. Also known as climate bonds, they are asset-linked and normally backed by issuer’s balance sheet. These come with tax incentives. They are often verified by a third party such as climate bond standard board. Global green bond issuance has already surpassed the \$100 billion mark.
2. Green Securitization: The process involves creation of financial instruments which are backed by financial assets like lease receivables or mortgages. These Asset backed bonds are then sold to investors and returns are based on the cash flows generated by underlying assets. In case of a green securitization the underlying cash flow is related to low carbon assets or the proceeds from the deal are to be invested in low carbon assets. Securitization helps institutional investors to fund small scale assets and small and medium scale business.
3. Green Sovereign Bonds: These bonds allow the government to tap capital markets to direct funds towards such related commitments and related policy measures. Netherlands sovereign bonds were the first sovereign green bonds issued by a European country to receive certification. European countries have shown increased interest in the issue of Sovereign Green Bonds. These bonds show a country’s commitment toward sustainable and low carbon growth strategies.
4. Green Project Bonds: The proceeds of these bonds are earmarked for specific projects and assets. Quality of asset that backs the project along with the return streams generated by it becoming the basis of credit rating of the bond. The Industrial Development Authority of the County of Pinal’s \$61.4 million green bond was the first renewable natural gas project financing in the US capital markets.

5. **Green Loan:** The loan is made to finance or refinance a whole or a part, new or existing Green Projects and includes Projects pertaining to environment like renewable energy, pollution prevention and control, climate change adaption and clean transportation. There are four Green Loan Principles: Use of Proceeds, Process of Project Evaluation and Selection, Management of Proceeds and Reporting. State Bank of India announced the country's first Green Car Loan in 2019.

Debt/Equity

1. **Green Sukuk:** These are Shari'ah compliant green investments. These Islamic bonds are in tune with the Shari'ah principles which prohibit interest. These have become very popular and are used both by the government and the corporate sector for raising finance. Shell MD (Malaysia) was the first to issue corporate Sukuk worth RM125 million, in 1990 and this was followed in 2001 by Bahrain.
2. **Green Perpetual Bond:** These bonds do not have a maturity date. The coupon payments are made forever and there is no redemption of the Principle. These are hybrid securities since they have both the characteristic of debt and equity instruments. Generally issuers set call dates 5-7 years after the bond issue so that they can redeem the bonds. The first perpetual bonds were issued by Xinjiang Goldwind, a Chinese wind turbine manufacturer, in 2016. The 6 Chinese issuers to date have raised the equivalent of USD1.7bn in 9 deals, primarily to finance investment in water and wastewater management and adaptation (USD976m) as well as renewable energy assets and related equipment (USD654m).
3. **Green Convertible Bond:** A convertible bond can be converted into a company's equity during the bond's life, normally at the discretion of the bondholder. The bond carries credit rating of the issuer. Tesla Motors, Inc. issue USD 600 million of Green Convertible Bonds in 2013. In 2019 Link Reit (Asia's biggest property investment trust) with an issue of USD 640 million became the world's first real estate company to issue such bond.
4. **Green Mezzanine Bond:** These bonds involve more risk than the other financing by financial institutions. The proceeds are allocated toward nominated assets and projects. A mezzanine finance facility of EUR245 million was provided by AMP capital to a French renewable energy provider Neoen.

Equity

1. **Public Private Partnership:** This type of partnership is used on a global level to help public project to attract private capital. However infrastructure projects are normally not financed through PPP. A significant amount of risk and responsibility is assumed by the private partner and their remuneration is performance based. PPP has become a very popular concept for green growth projects. PT Sarana Multi Infrastruktur (PT SMI), a state-owned infrastructure financing company, plays an active role in facilitating infrastructure financing, project development and infrastructure advisory services in Indonesia.
2. **Private Equity:** Green Private Equity firms supply venture capital to projects promoting sustainability and green growth. These investments are important for promoting a low carbon economy. Zen Ecosystems' series-B funding round attracted a funding of AUD5m from the Clean Energy Innovation Fund, in April 2017.
3. **Joint Venture:** A Joint Venture is where two or more entities combine their resources, while still maintaining their individual identity, towards a project. The partnership remains during the duration of the project and they agree to share costs, profits and losses related to the project. A joint venture deal being made between Temasek (Singapore) and Swedish private equity

group EQT aiming to launch a new renewable energy platform for India. The main goal of this deal will be on building wind and solar farms and asset acquisitions.

4. Investment Trust: These funds are publicly listed and are treated as shares. These may have tax advantages. In 2006 Jupiter Asset Management launched Jupiter Green Investment Trust in UK. The Trust launched open-ended Jupiter Ecology fund in 1986.

Credit Enhancement

1. Guarantees: A credit guarantee absorbs partial or full debt service default risk. A political risk guarantee covers private investors and lenders from lending risks associated with sovereign or sub sovereign borrowers. Partial Swap Guarantees cover the investor from currency exchange rate risk in case of cross-border transactions and different debt and deal currency.
2. A/B Loans or Grants: The loan amount is divided in two parts where portion 'A' is offered by a multilateral development bank in order to attract other lenders towards the 'B' tranche. The MDB becomes the lead lender and administrative agent. Italian transmissions system operator Terna issued a USD81m green loan in project finance format in July 2017. The Inter-American Development Bank offered the USD56m. A loan and BBVA subscribed a B loan for USD25m. The deal will finance the design and construction of a 213km transmission line of 500kv in the north-east of Uruguay.
3. First-Loss Capital: Wherein an investor or a grant maker agrees that he will bear the first losses of an investment in order to make the investment more attractive to other participants which would have avoided the deal otherwise. For example the AUD 100 million investment in Australian Prime Property Fund commercial made by The Clean energy Finance Corporation.
4. Viability-Gap Funding: There may be certain projects which are feasible on the economic fund but financially they lack funds. VGF refers to the one time grant that is provided to such projects to make the financially viable. In 2004 the government of India had launched a VGF for public-private partnership infrastructure projects. The same was also used to set up 5,000MW grid-connected solar PV Projects.

III. India and Green Finance

India's journey in the field of green finance is at a nascent stage. It is crucial to link the financial sector to this cause in order to make it responsive to climate related concerns. The two aspects of Green Funding are as follows:

1. Financial institutions ensuring (before granting any credit) that no project financed breaches current environmental standards.
2. Prefer activities or projects that are climate-friendly ie, ones that reduce emissions or help cope with vagaries of climate change.

Despite the concept being rather new certain institutions like the State Bank of India, Axis Bank, Power Finance Corporation and other independent institutions like Renew Power and Greenko have issued green bonds to tap into available green funds. During 2012-2018 India's green bond issuance was around \$7.7 bn, making it the second largest issuer of green bonds within emerging markets in that period, according to RBI's Trend and Progress of Banking in India Report 2018-19. As per Bloomberg New Energy Finance Report, India ranks second globally in attractiveness for renewable sector investments. Mainly due to its policy push towards increasing renewable energy. Moreover it had the second largest (2017) renewable energy investment market amongst such climate-conscious economies and it also attracted \$ 9.4 billion of fresh funding.

Still as per environment ministry estimates India will need \$2.5 trillion in order to meet climate change targets. In the next 5 years green infrastructure alone will demand \$280 bn. India is setting its eye on the Electric vehicle segment and incentives are being offered. NITI Aayog has set an ambitious target of 40-80% EV penetration in different consumer segments, but this would entail creating the adequate charging infrastructure and investments in storage technologies to reduce upfront costs. The government's plan to build gigafactories (Tesla-style) in India, will have a budgeted cost of approximately \$5 billion. Green finance at an affordable cost will be the pre-requisite of such plans. In order to tackle climate change for this decade India will need 3 times the total investment that it has already made in a period of 10 years in the infrastructure sector. The various investment opportunities in India pertaining to climate are as follows:

Investment Opportunity	Value (in USD)
Transport electric vehicles	322 million
Transport infrastructure	615 million
Green Buildings	390 million
Renewable Energy	403.7 billion
Municipal solid waste	11 billion
Climate smart agriculture	194 billion
Climate smart urban water	86 million
Large Hydro	44 billion

Source: IFC

Finance Challenges

To achieve its Nationally Determined Targets, India would need USD2.5 trillion by 2030 and in order to fulfill its Sustainable Development Goals USD960 billion are required on an annual basis. These targets would need contribution from the private and development finance.

Long Term vs Short Term

1. Lending: There is an asset-liability mismatch. Sustainable development finance is highly dependent on the Indian Banks which have to work under certain constraints like exposure norms and CAR specified by the Reserve Bank of India. Sustainable infrastructure finance draws heavily from the banking sector however the RBI requirements place a cap on the infrastructure exposure. Moreover infrastructure loans are for a longer duration (10-15 years) and the capital raised by banks are dependent on the deposits (1-2 years) thus ending up in a mismatch of asset and liabilities. Other sources like pension and insurance funds, which are of a longer duration should be tapped for such projects.
2. Investing: The market actors work on short-term and profit basis. Thus long term risks due to climate change are left unrecognized. This may lead to asset mispricing which may result in long term costs and losses.
3. Understanding Sustainable Finance: A clear understanding of Sustainable finance becomes difficult because a globally accepted standard definition is unavailable. This leads to a high possibility of a green wash. Lack of clarity in strategy and multiple shareholders and instruments make the situation more complex. Universally accepted guidelines are required to streamline the process.
4. No tracking and monitoring mechanism: Lack of structure makes it difficult to efficiently track and monitor fund flows. A reliable monitoring and accounting framework is required e.g. South Africa has developed MRV system to track mitigation, adaption and financing. Such models help analyze data to ensure the achievement of climate goals.

Innovative Challenges

1. **Capital Markets:** Capital markets play a very crucial role in every economy. These markets fulfill the capital requirements of infrastructural projects. The Indian bond market lacks depth and volume and there are limited options when it comes to raising long term debt. There is a need to strengthen the municipal market and consistent standards of accounting and disclosure need to be established.
2. **Market Instruments:** There is a dearth of innovative financial instruments to revolutionize green financing. Blended finance and impact investing are of utmost importance to mobilize substantial amount of sustainable finance from various sources like government, philanthropists and organizational investors. The products should be made as per various sector requirements e.g. securitization of long term assets is suitable for sectors like renewable energy.
3. **Incentives:** It is important to incentivize sustainable financial decisions for a better success rate. These incentives seem to be missing in the Indian Financial System. Along with providing custom made financial products and services it is also important to provide certain incentives to the investors.

Policy Challenges

1. **Government:** Even after more than a decade of launching the National Action Plan on climate change there is no clear MRV structure for international and domestic climate finance. There is a lack of coordination within the ministries which makes the implementation of plans difficult. There is limited engagement with private players for development of funding and regulation. The current mechanisms of funding, regulation and incentives fall short due to lack of proper implementation.
2. **Regulatory Policy:** Basel norms limit the exposure to certain sectors to ensure better management of risk, this has resulted in some constraints from the supply side since banks are the primary lenders of sustainable finance. The current financial system does not provide a framework to include important aspects like environment accounting framework and environment and social risk management. Even though SEBI has made disclosures mandatory for green bonds but there is still ambiguity in the definition of 'green'.

Recommendations (India)

Product-centric Measures

1. **Strengthen the Green Bond Market:** On a global scale Green Bonds are one of the most crucial vehicles of green finance. India is one of the top 10 green bond markets with a cumulative issue USD3.8 billion (2017). Renewable energy garners 68% of those proceeds, 21% towards low carbon transport and 10% towards energy efficiency and green buildings. Regulatory bodies like SEBI need to provide more comprehensive outlines to further strengthen the market in order to attract more finance. Further policy measure are required like exempting CRR and SLR from green financing, increasing limits under Section 80 C for green bond investments and make the registration process easy for global investors.
2. **Tap the Municipal Bond Market:** These bonds have existed over two decades but the market remains under-utilized. Except for large cities, other urban bodies do not make their accounts public. Disclosure is the key requirement for bonds issue so it is important to ensure scrutiny of financial performance of these bodies and improving debt management to ensure investor faith and interest in Indian Municipal Bonds. There should be alignment of these bonds with smart cities and AMRUT scheme targets.
3. **Blended Finance:** Blended Finance is the future of development. It used public and philanthropic capital in order to catalyze private investment. India has a huge potential as far as philanthropic

funding is concerned. This can be effectively tapped thus increasing the corpus of sustainable finance. As per survey(2016) of 74 blended finance vehicles by the World Economic Forum, every USD1 of public capital attracts USD1-20 of private investment. But the effectiveness of blended finance is dependent on effective monitoring and evaluation.

4. Use Credit Enhancement: This method makes the project more attractive by boosting credit rating through reduction in credit risk and lowering the interest rate. Under the “Credit Enhancement Scheme” by IIFCL, 5 year tenor bonds have been launched for funding of infrastructure projects. This financial solution has helped Renew Power and Hindustan Power. Though the scheme has been helpful but there is still a need for involvement by Public Sector Banks.
5. SDG aligned bonds: These bonds are innovative instruments which follow a holistic approach of sustainable financing. The World Bank was the first to launch bonds linked to SDGs in 2017 in order to support sustainable use of fresh and salt water. India needs such innovative instruments to boost investment especially from the private players at a national level.
6. Leverage Securitization: This helps to pool larger projects with smaller projects in order to reap the benefits of risk diversification. This helps to ensure better finance opportunities, a lower cost of capital and helps to secure institutional investor participation. Securitization has a lot of scope in India and it should be adopted to better utilization domestic investment base.
7. Sovereign Bonds: In 2016, Poland was the first country to issue such bonds (EUR 750 billion). A lot of capital is still needed for the infrastructure sector so India can use sovereign bonds to fill the gap.
8. Rupee Denominated Bonds: RDBs avoid exchange rate risk so they can effectively channelize funds private funds towards sustainable sectors. Masala bonds are available in offshore markets. They are denominated in Indian currency instead of the local currency of the country they are placed in. These help the global investors to effectively invest in emerging markets.
9. Impact investing: Impact investing can accelerate the financing process and help progress on social grounds. As per a Global Impact Investing Network Report this method has improved 60-80 million lives in this country.

Develop and Implement Practices

1. Carbon-stress testing: In India climate change is not included in stress tests. Industrial and Commercial bank of China has developed a stress test inclusive of climate change. Such practices must be taken up by India.
2. Transparency and Accountability: Mandatory CSR disclosures in India have promoted better monitoring and reporting requirements however there is no penalty for non-disclosure. Similar to the credit rating process the organizations must be rated on non-financial parameters.
3. ESG risk management: ESG criteria should become a part of the lending process. Currently there is no process or guideline to promote ESG criteria in the Indian Banking Sector. The banks should develop capacities and train professionals to include ESG risks in lending.
4. Capacity building and knowledge sharing: There is a need to provide adequate understanding to investors and bankers regarding risks in sectors like sustainable agriculture, water management and other sustainable business.
5. Climate Literacy: Climate education can have a major impact in building an environmentally sustainable society. Innovative means should be sought to ensure the production process is carried through environment friendly means. Start-ups can play a very significant role in coming up with sustainable and environment friendly solutions.
6. Form specialized institution: Either a new framework should be established or institutions like IREDA should be transformed into green banks. This will help to empower urban and rural communities and help meet the environmental targets of investors and the government

Conclusion

Climate change is a stark reality and no government or institution can work in isolation. A strengthening of commitment on the global landscape has ushered the way for green finance. As the economy evolves many innovative financial instruments have been developed over the years to help bridge the funding gap. The India dream of a USD 5 trillion economy by 2024 depends on the GDP growth. The investment climate of the country has to factor in the impact of climate change. There is a strong push towards sustainable development goal commitment. Despite various initiatives an annual gap of USD 2.5 trillion still poses as the biggest hurdle. To develop and strengthen the financial eco-system a series of measures are required like increase in transparency, promoting innovative technologies, coordinated policy making, low carbon benchmarks and green standards. The 'Green' Indian journey has already begun and it needs collective efforts of all the stakeholders to reach the desired goals.

References

1. Flammer Caroline, Corporate Green Bonds, SSRN, (July 5, 2018). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3125518>
2. Wang, Yao and Zhi, Qiang, The Role of Green Finance in Environmental Protection: Two Aspects of Market Mechanism and Policies, Energy Procedia (Volume 104), December 2016, pp.31-316 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2016.12.053>
3. DuPont, Carolyn and Levitt, James and Bilmes, Linda, Green Bonds and Land Conservation: The Evolution of a New Financing Tool. HKS Working Paper No. 072.(December 7, 2015). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2700311>
4. Chowdhury, Tasnim&Datta, Rajib&Mohajan, Haradhan, Green finance is essential for economic development and sustainability,MPRA Paper 51169, University Library of Munich, Germany, revised (June9, 2013).
5. Agrawal, Shrija (August 11, 2019). The urgent case for green finance. Live mint, Retrieved from <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/the-urgent-case-for-green-finance-1565535551655.html>
6. Bhattacharya, Sandeep and Jain Megha (June 21, 2019). Unlock India's green funding potential. The pioneer, Retrieved from <https://www.dailypioneer.com/2019/columnists/unlock-india---s-green-funding-potential.html>
7. Aiyer Sourajit (October 23, 2019) How Can India Scale-Up Green Finance? Youth Ki Awaaz. Retrieved from <https://www.youthkiawaaz.com/2019/10/targeted-policies-to-scale-up-green-finance-in-india/>
8. Huges, Tony (June 7, 2019). Climate Change Stress Testing. GARP. Retrieved from <https://www.moodyanalytics.com/-/media/article/2019/climate-change-stress-testing.pdf>
9. IEA (2019), "World Energy Investment 2019", IEA, Paris, Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-investment-2019>
10. Krushelnyska, Olha. Introduction to Green Finance. Global Environment Facility. Retrieved from <https://www.thegef.org/sites/default/files/events/Intro%20to%20Green%20Finance.pdf>